

SmartDepth: Motion-Aware Depth Prediction with Intelligent Computing for Navigation

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Abstract—Advancements in robotic platforms emphasize the need for efficient algorithm designs that minimize resource usage for sensing and computing. However, this objective clashes with the complexity of advanced perception tasks that are essential to robotics operations, such as depth perception and navigation. In this paper, we present *SmartDepth*, a new perception and navigation framework that significantly reduces resource usage compared to traditional approaches. *SmartDepth* considers a navigation model whose logic requires a chain of depth maps for a sequential number of steps. At its core, *SmartDepth* leverages highly accurate DNN-predicted depth maps to initialize the chain. To optimize resource efficiency, it then employs Motion-Aware Depth Prediction (MADP)—our novel, low-complexity, geometry-based algorithm—to extrapolate high-quality depth maps for the rest of the chain. The length of a chain is determined by a predefined efficiency level and should be set to ensure that the quality of MADP-predicted depth maps remains useful. In fact, extending the chain beyond this point would result in degradation, rendering the predicted depth maps ineffective. Experimental results show that, compared to a state-of-the-art navigation framework that uses relatively expensive depth extraction as each step, *SmartDepth* effectively reduces computational costs, in the form of execution time by 19%, average power consumption by 26%, and energy expenditure by 20%, and at a nominal degradation in navigation accuracy of 0.98% and a small increase in path length of 12%. While larger computational savings can potentially be obtained, this comes with a larger degradation in navigation accuracy and path length. Thus, we posit that *SmartDepth* is an intuitive evolution in perception-based robotics that improves computing efficiency, with a controlled accuracy loss.

Index Terms—Depth estimation, deep neural network, resource optimization, sensing, robotics, navigation, autonomy, machine learning, artificial intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Depth maps and object segmentation are essential for perception-based decision making, such as navigation, robotics, and autonomy. Deep Neural Networks (DNN) have become the State-of-the-Art (SotA) approach for extracting these environmental cues. Despite advances in real-time monocular depth prediction and segmentation [1]–[3], these methods typically require image input for every frame. When executing several consecutive frames, this approach leads to

Fig. 1. High level overview of using MADP to make one depth map prediction at time t , and at a proposed camera pose, based on the previous two steps.

significant power consumption and possibly excessive processing time, due to the computational complexity of high-performance DNNs. The high demands in power and time clash with the characteristics of resource-constrained platforms such as drones and other smaller vehicles and robotic platforms, where computational resources should be used sparingly due to limited energy reservoirs and lightweight hardware. Furthermore, excessive time spent extracting depth maps from the scene can degrade the reaction time of the vehicle. There is a growing need for low-complexity approaches that strike a balance between efficiency and accuracy.

This paper introduces a novel technique that leverages sensory input from previous frames to predict the future depth map before the camera reaches a specific location. This capability can be used both to reduce resource usage, at the cost of a controlled performance degradation and to improve navigation performance. Fig. 1 illustrates a single prediction based on the proposed framework – referenced as the Motion-Aware Depth Prediction (MADP) algorithm. MADP leverages previous 2D depth map(s), and optionally object segmentation maps, to extrapolate a depth map at any given time and location. The segmentation maps are used to update the depths even when moving objects are present, a feature that can be turned off, further reducing computational complexity. A

downstream navigation model takes as input a combination of DNN- and MADP-predicted depth maps to navigate to a target position. *SmartDepth* denotes the technique behind switching between a depth perception model and MADP. It can be scaled by intelligently selecting an efficiency level before runtime – as determined by considerations in expected energy expenditure, execution time, mean power, depth error, navigation accuracy, and path length.

A. Contributions

The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- We present a geometric algorithm, Motion-Aware Depth Predictor (MADP), that leverages relative camera poses and previous frames to predict future depth maps at arbitrary positions in time and space. We show this to be computationally more efficient than using SotA DNN models at each step.
- We present *SmartDepth*, an algorithm that switches between expensive depth perception models and our more efficient MADP algorithm, as controlled by an efficiency level that sets how long to use MADP before refreshing to the more accurate depth perception models. This level should be set to that where the error is known to exceed a known threshold.
- We implement the MADP algorithm using the real world dataset for car autonomy, KITTI [4], to benchmark our approach in terms of expected depth prediction error, execution time, power consumption, and energy expenditure – as evaluated on an NVIDIA Jetson Xavier.
- We implement *SmartDepth* using the drone simulator Microsoft AirSim [5], to evaluate the impact of *SmartDepth* on a navigation model, where degradations in depth error predictions will manifest themselves as degradations in navigation accuracy and found path length. Thus, providing a means for selecting an efficiency level for *SmartDepth*.

We observe that MADP has a monotonically decreasing error in depth prediction when increasing the prediction distance, in either time or space. Using AirSim, we determine an optimal distance to predict into the future is 16 meters, resulting in a slight decrease in navigation accuracy of 0.98% and an increase in path length of 12.19%, as compared to using a SotA depth model at each step. The advantage in using *SmartDepth*, is that we observe a mean reduction in expected computational costs, in the form of execution time by 19%, average power consumption by 26%, and energy expenditure by 20%, and at a nominal degradation in navigation accuracy of 0.98% and small increase in path length of 12%.

II. RELATED WORK

The literature is abundant with SotA deep neural network (DNN) models for depth estimation using monocular cameras. MonoDepth [6], [7] was revolutionary in this area, paving the way for more evolved models such as LPG [8] and GCNDepth [9]. In LPG, the authors enhance monocular depth estimation with a novel "local planar guidance" (LPG) representation, incorporating LPG layers at multiple decoding stages for more accurate depth maps. This approach achieves state-of-the-art results on datasets like KITTI, outperforming previous

methods in accuracy and robustness. In GCNDepth, the authors improve self-supervised monocular depth estimation by using Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) to capture object geometry and spatial relationships. Their model, with two auto-encoders (ResNet-50 for depth and ResNet-18 for ego-motion), achieves 89% accuracy on KITTI and Make3D, while reducing trainable parameters by 40% compared to existing methods. From a performance standpoint, both LPG and GCNDepth provide a balance of computational efficiency and high accuracy, theoretically enabling the application of these approaches in constrained environments. Another key area of current state-of-the-art (SotA) research focuses on extracting object segmentation maps from images. When combined with depth maps, these segmentation outputs enable the estimation of relative object positions with respect to the vehicle's camera pose. Herein, we employ Mask R-CNN model [10] with ResNet-50 backbone [11] implemented in the Torchvision library [12] to perform instance segmentation. Additionally, we employed a Mask R-CNN model with a lightweight ResNet-18 backbone [11], pre-trained on the Microsoft COCO dataset [13]. We utilize these models to improve depth predictions by track moving objects.

Conversely, only a few SotA navigation frameworks directly integrate 2D depth maps or images into their logic. Their typical structure consists of using a lightweight neural network trained with various versions of sensor inputs. For example, CMP [14] integrates 2D-mapping and planning into a unified framework, where mapping is guided by the planner's needs. It uses spatial memory to handle incomplete observations and generates a top-down belief map of the world, which helps the agent track visited areas and plan actions. Most notably, some solutions deployed in Microsoft AirSim that take input: directly from on-board depth sensors [15], extracted depths from a monocular camera using a DNN [16], and event-based sensors [17]. We aim to build on these SotA approaches by introducing a more effective strategy of obtaining the depth maps for input into a navigation model.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a vehicle with a forward-facing monocular camera, navigating from a start to a target position while determining its relative location (*e.g.*, via GPS). Depth maps and pose data inform the navigation model, which selects motion actions at each step. *SmartDepth* aims to optimize path length, avoid collisions, and minimize computation. At each step, the vehicle either uses (a) an accurate but costly DNN-based depth estimation or (b) the efficient MADP algorithm, which extrapolates depths from recent frames before executing the navigation model. Fig. 2 illustrates the system model. *SmartDepth* chooses between two pipelines, $A \rightarrow C$ or $B \rightarrow C$, at each step. Each pipeline has associated resource costs and depth prediction errors. Pipeline $A \rightarrow C$ represents the current state-of-the-art navigation approach, where depth maps are predicted from an input camera image using a DNN, and the results are fed into a downstream navigation model. Pipeline $B \rightarrow C$ is a lower-complexity option that

Fig. 2. SmartDepth system model, illustrating the various pipelines to select from, either $A \rightarrow C$ or $B \rightarrow C$, in one observe-compute-action step.

uses the MADP algorithm for depth predictions, reducing computational costs but with lower depth prediction accuracy, which may affect navigation performance. Option A2 can run in parallel with $A \rightarrow C$ to predict an object segmentation map, which helps improve depth prediction when moving objects are present. *SmartDepth*'s logic determines, at each step, which pipeline to use and how to select from each queue.

IV. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Formally, we define the optimization problem for *SmartDepth* as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \arg \min_X (\langle \dot{E} \rangle) \\ & \text{s.t. } \langle \eta(X) \rangle \geq \beta * \langle \eta_{DNN} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here, X is a static value set before runtime, determining the maximum distance from a reference frame that MADP (pipeline $B \rightarrow C$) can be used before switching to pipeline $A \rightarrow C$ for a new reference frame. $\langle \dot{E} \rangle$ is the expected energy expended per navigation path, $\langle \eta_{DNN} \rangle$ is the number of successful test paths when using a DNN at each step, $\langle \eta(X) \rangle$ is the number of successful paths using MADP with a given X , and β (between 0 and 1) is a scalar setting the acceptable threshold for unsuccessful paths (e.g., 0.99 allows a 1% decrease in navigation accuracy).

We solve this optimization problem by training several navigation models using reinforcement learning with different values of X . Each trained model is then evaluated on a test set to determine the optimal static value of X that satisfies our constraint. Additionally, we establish basic logic to determine when to switch between using the MADP algorithm and a more expensive depth perception operation.

Fig. 3. MADP Flow Chart. The yellow boxes and yellow dashed lines indicate additional components for dynamic mode, while the rest represent static mode.

V. MOTION-AWARE DEPTH PREDICTOR (MADP)

Fig. 3 illustrates the general structure of the MADP algorithm that is used to predict a depth map at a given frame at step t , w.r.t. a reference frame at step t' . The algorithm operates in two modes: the first assumes a static scene with no moving objects, while the second incorporates the Object Velocity Detector to handle dynamic scenes involving moving objects. MADP first projects 2D depth map pixels into a 3D space. The dynamic mode also calculates detected object velocities between frames t' and $t' - 1$, then the 3D points corresponding to moving objects are adjusted to their predicted positions at frame t . In both modes, 3D points are then projected back onto the camera's pixel coordinates from the perspective of the future frame to generate a predicted 2D depth map. This can continue for several frames.

A. Depth Prediction in Static Scenes

In this default mode, objects in the scene are considered static such that they will not make movements that significantly affect depth predictions. Herein, we refer to projecting between 2D space (from depth images) to 3D space (global coordinates), and between a reference and future frame.

Given reference 2D depths $\mathbf{D}^{(t')}$ at frame t' , the value at each pixel, (j, k) , as indexed by (row, column) of the image, is mapped from the 2D image space to 3D global space using:

$$P_i^{(t')} = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{R}_{t' \rightarrow \mathcal{O}} \cdot \mathbf{K}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{D}_{j',k'}^{(t')} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} j' \\ k' \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{r}_{t' \rightarrow \mathcal{O}} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the constant intrinsic camera matrix, and P is the set of coordinates to the corresponding pixels as observed from 3D global space – such that the i^{th} item in the set corresponds to a set of $[x, y, z]$ coordinates that has some physical entity occupying that space with a resolution determined by \mathbf{K} . Quantities \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{r} are the rotation matrix and translation vector needed to transform the camera pose at frame t' into the global coordinate system – given the global origin \mathcal{O} .

The 3D points are then transformed into a future depth map at frame t , by setting the pixel values at $\mathbf{D}_{j,k}^{(t)}$ for all points in the set $P^{(t')}$ that are still in scope, using:

$$\begin{bmatrix} j \\ k \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \text{round}(\mathbf{K} \cdot \left(\mathbf{R}_{\mathcal{O} \rightarrow t} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{r}_{\mathcal{O} \rightarrow t} \right)) \quad (3)$$

where j and k are rounded to the nearest integer. Distant objects will intuitively occupy fewer pixels. As the camera moves forward, these objects appear closer but remain under-sampled, leading to a loss of detail. Increasing the depth map resolution or incorporating additional depth maps during the 3D point-gathering phase can mitigate this effect.

B. Object Velocity Detector

Fig. 4. Velocity Detector Flow Chart.

The object velocity detector obtains 3D coordinates of predicted anchor points for objects between two consecutive frames, and then calculates their displacements. Fig. 4 illustrates the entire process. A set of object masks, M , for each frame are generated using a DNN. The l^{th} mask in the set contains a list of pixels which correspond to the l^{th} detected object. Traditional feature extraction algorithms can align key points that have similar patterns within two consecutive RGB images. Since consecutive frames are temporally close, their visual differences are small, allowing the use of ORB [18], which is a relatively lightweight algorithm that determines several key points for each detected object. Each key point is a pair of pixels that are linked between two images.

For key points, $P_i^{(t')}$ and $P_i^{(t'-1)}$, between two consecutive reference frames which contain the l^{th} detected object, we calculate the object's velocity using:

$$V_i = (P_i^{(t'-1)} - P_i^{(t')}) / \Delta t \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta v = \frac{\|\mathbf{v}^{(a)} - \mathbf{v}^{(b)}\|}{\|\mathbf{v}^{(a)}\| + \|\mathbf{v}^{(b)}\|}, \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta \theta = \cos(\theta_{a,b}) = \frac{\mathbf{v}^{(a)} \cdot \mathbf{v}^{(b)}}{\|\mathbf{v}^{(a)}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{v}^{(b)}\|}. \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{v}^{(a)}$ and $\mathbf{v}^{(b)}$ are the velocities corresponding to two arbitrary pairs of key points for a given object, as found by ORB. We compared multiple velocities from the same object, but at different key point pairs, for two reasons: (1) to check if the object is valid, and (2) if the object is either moving or still. If velocities vary too much between different keypoints, then this reflects erratic behavior and we consider the object invalid – this is a means to discard false positive objects that are detected from the segmentation DNN. If the object is valid, we then consider it as moving only if the velocities are above some threshold. We determined these threshold values empirically, through trial and error, and the effectiveness of chosen values should vary across different domains.

C. Depth Prediction in Dynamic Scenes

MADP predicts depth in dynamic scenes by integrating the Object Velocity Detector into the static MADP framework. The global 3D points of moving objects are updated using their corresponding velocities, as shown in Fig. 3. After transforming the input depth maps into global 3D points, moving objects are identified and segmented from the background using object masks provided by the segmentation DNN. For each detected object, all corresponding global points are translated using the calculated velocity to account for motion:

$$\{P_i^{(t)} = P_i^{(t')} + V_i \cdot \Delta t \mid \forall i \in M_l \mid \forall M_l \in M\} \quad (7)$$

where Δt is the time between frames t and t' . Object points are projected onto the 2D image plane first and take priority, followed by background points, using Equation 3.

VI. SMARTDEPTH AND NAVIGATION

The navigation model f_θ is tasked with finding a path for a given start and target position, that minimizes the path length and avoids collisions. The path length is defined as the total number of steps taken from start to target. We also define the navigation accuracy, η , as the number of evaluation paths that successfully reached the target within a given threshold (set to two meters), within a maximum number of steps (two times the optimal ground truth path found before run-time), without collisions, and without leaving the bounds of the map. We make the assumption that the vehicle is a small resource-constrained device, with limited knowledge of the environment. Thus, we assume the vehicle only has a forward-facing monocular camera and a GPS. The navigation model f_θ uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) following the structure of that which was used to learn how to play Atari games in [19]. This structure allows for both multi-band 2D image input and 1D variables. The 1D variables are injected into the flattened layers after all of the convolutional layers of the CNN. We then use reinforcement learning to train the navigation model to predict motion actions at each step.

A. Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)

We train the navigation model f_θ using a double Deep Q-Network (DQN) [20], as implemented with the third party python library Stable Baselines 3 [21]. Each subsection below details the needed parameters to properly execute such an implementation. A DQN is, at its core, a neural network that operates by using a continuous input observation space, and a discrete output action space, and is trained following a loss function based on a user-defined reward function.

Note that DRL is sensitive to hyperparameters and random seeds. Thus, we use random restarts, typically used in local search algorithms, to independently train f_θ for a number of runs (we use ten) by keeping a given configuration of hyperparameters fixed but changing the random seed for each run. We keep the trained model corresponding to the run with the highest navigation accuracy. We trained each model for two million steps, utilizing a curriculum learning schedule that

incrementally increases the expected difficulty of randomly generated start and target positions used for training.

B. Reward Function

We empirically find a robust reward function that is a combination of rewards and penalties at varying degrees of magnitude, by: heavily penalizing collisions and rewarding reaching the target position, moderately penalizing moving out of bounds from the map and reaching the maximum number of steps, and slightly rewarding making progress towards the target and penalizing for each additional step taken along the path. Specifically, we use the following reward function:

$$r = \begin{cases} -10 & \text{collision} \\ -1 & \text{out of bounds or max steps} \\ 10 & \text{goal} \\ 0.1 * \tanh(\Delta d) - 0.1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where Δd is the change in relative Euclidean distance to the target position since the last step.

C. Observation Space

Inputs at each step into the navigation model are observations measured from the following observation space:

- A 2D predicted depth map observed from the current pose, either: (a) extracted from an image using a DNN or (b) extrapolated using the MADP algorithm. Each pixel is linearly normalized between 0.1 and 1, where 1 is considered to be the horizon at 255 meters, or greater, away from the vehicle and 0 is reserved for missing data such as invalid pixels from MADP.
- The relative Euclidean distance between the current position of the vehicle and the target position. This is a scalar value linearly normalized between 0 and 1, where 1 is considered to be at the horizon at 255 meters.
- The relative yaw between the direction the vehicle is currently facing and the target position. This is a scalar value linearly normalized between 0 and 1, where 0 is just below -180 degrees and 1 is +180 degrees.
- The previous B -many steps for each of the items above.

The depth map resolution is kept relatively small at 36x64 pixels to reduce computational complexity. We found a value of $B = 3$ to be robust, which follows literature [19]. Thus our observation space has dimensions of 4x36x64 for the 2D variables, and 1x8 for the 1D variables.

D. Action Space

The output layer of the navigation model’s neural network contains relative likelihoods pertaining to which action to take among several predetermined options. Each output node of the neural network corresponds to a different action, and the discrete output action from the navigation model is that corresponding to the highest output value. We consider only horizontal motion, as this can be applied to several types of vehicles and robotics. We use coordinates typical to robotics

applications, so that $+x$ is facing forward from the vehicle (regardless of its yaw), and $+y$ is facing to the right of the vehicle. There are seven actions for the DQN to select from: rotate 90 degrees about the z -axis either clockwise or counter-clockwise, or move forward at a fixed speed by Δx meters – where Δx can be either 2, 4, 8, 16, or 32.

A cycle restarts after each action, and the system will continue to take observe-compute-action steps until the vehicle reaches one of its termination criteria as defined in Section VI. Note that the forward motion step sizes are in terms of distance, Δx , since we primarily are focused on depth estimation in this paper, but the navigation frequency of steps can be translated in terms of time using Equation 9:

$$\Delta x * f = v \quad (9)$$

where f is the cycle frequency as measured in Hertz, and v is the vehicle’s speed. From this perspective, a forward action can be considered as: “continue along the current trajectory at speed v ”, and Δx determines a variable frame rate at which we observe depth maps and compute a full step.

E. SmartDepth

We aim to solve the optimization problem defined in Equation 1 to select an optimal static value of X . This is accomplished using empirical testing and statistical analysis. We find it necessary to hard code in *SmartDepth*’s logic to refresh the DNN depth predictions using the $A \rightarrow C$ pipeline after using either of the actions that rotate the yaw of the vehicle. This is intuitive since the perspective will have a drastic change when rotating the pose of the camera by 90 degrees. The non-intuitive portion is after how many forward steps to use the more accurate pipeline $A \rightarrow C$ over the lower-cost pipeline $B \rightarrow C$. We explore this space in our results section, where the answer to this question is determined by the value of β used in Equation 1.

VII. RESULTS

Here we introduce our test bed environments used to train and/or test our model pipelines. Then we present results of our core MADP pipelines, to illustrate both the depth prediction prowess and the trade-off between navigation accuracy and efficiency. We explore the hyper-parameter space and highlight significant outcomes and findings.

A. KITTI Testbed

The KITTI dataset [4] is a widely used benchmark dataset for autonomous driving research, providing high-quality sensor data collected from real-world driving scenarios. KITTI includes several key sensor modalities, such as stereo cameras, LiDAR, and GPS/IMU. KITTI captures real-world complexities, including occlusions, varying lighting conditions, and diverse urban and rural scenes, which are crucial for testing the robustness of depth prediction methods. This algorithm leverages IMU data provided by KITTI to accurately determine the camera’s location, and the prediction results are evaluated on the ground truth depth provided by LiDAR.

B. Microsoft AirSim Testbed

Microsoft AirSim [5] is a drone simulator, complete with several parameters related to available sensors, such as cameras and LiDARS, and environmental factors, such as cars, roads, houses, foliage, lighting, and weather. AirSim is built on Unreal Engine [22], which is used to render physics and graphics. AirSim is a robust environment for research purposes, because of its access to ground truths pulled directly from Unreal Engine and dynamic ability to move anywhere on the map and collect observations. As opposed to static datasets, where not only is a researcher constrained to using the data points captured during real-time data collection, but real world datasets are also more prone to error and may be lacking in the availability and accuracy of ground truths. This limits the ability to train navigation models on real-world static datasets, and is why we use AirSim to this end. We maintain both a real-world dataset and simulator to obtain realistic benchmarks on the MADP algorithm, while also being able to obtain navigation results with AirSim.

C. Execution Cost

We conduct benchmarking on an NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier Developer Kit (P2972), using NVIDIA’s native JetPack™ SDK as an operating system, and the Jetson Stats package (jtop) to specifically benchmark power levels. Benchmarking was conducted independently for each model by first loading it onto the Xavier and executing one frame to mitigate warming-up effects, then averaging both the execution time and consumed power over several consecutive frames. Energy is calculated by power multiplied by time. We find that using BTS for depth predictions, at each frame, results in a mean execution time of 0.3882 seconds and a power consumption of 23.88 Watts, per frame. Using MADP has a significantly lower execution time of 0.0103 seconds and power consumption of 10.34 Watts. This results in a substantial reduction in energy expenditure, per frame, on average, by 98.85%. Thus, switching from using BTS to MADP, for even one frame, will have a significant reduction in computing costs.

D. MADP

To assess prediction accuracy, we used a set of 16 image sequences from the KITTI dataset, covering the ‘city’, ‘residential’, and ‘road’ scene categories, totaling 15,430 images. All results were based on using a single depth map as input.

Fig. 5 plots the extracted depth value from a DNN versus the extrapolated value from the MADP (dynamic) algorithm. Here, Δt determines how many frames ahead the prediction is made. As reported, the error increases with depth, which is acceptable since objects closer to the vehicle are more critical for navigation. Additionally, the MADP algorithm tends to slightly underestimate the predicted depths, which is a safer approach to prevent potential collisions with objects that might be inaccurately perceived as farther away.

Fig. 6 shows the Mean Absolute Percent Error (MAPE) for depth predictions, as a function of Δt . We compare the performance against the “Compare” baseline, where the latest

Fig. 5. Heat map showing densities of single pixels, taken from frames that are sampled from several test paths. There are up to 10,000 pixels in each bin on the x-axis, at ten-meter intervals. This uses the following modules: KITTI dataset, GCNDepth, Mask R-CNN with ResNet-50, MADP (dynamic).

Fig. 6. Error for different model pipelines, illustrating depth prediction degradation as a function of Δt , the future time step. “Compare” refers to using the same depth map at the reference frame for all future predictions.

DNN-generated depth map is used as the predicted depth for the target future frame. This is a typical metric used in forecasting temporal data to use as a comparative baseline technique, as it can be a difficult metric to outperform. All of our MADP methods successfully outperformed the “Compare” approach. We partition results into two ranges, (0-10] and (10-80] meter ranges, to highlight differences in predicting pixels that are near versus far. While error increases consistently with each future step across all methods, static MADP exhibits a slower error growth within the 0-10 meter range.

Although the dynamic mode shows no significant advantage in average error, this is largely due to static objects outnumbering moving objects by a factor of 50. A challenge we encountered is the misclassification of static objects as moving, leading to additional errors. However, when ground truth depth maps are used as input (such as from LiDAR for KITTI), we notice that false positives are largely eliminated. Furthermore, in sequences where moving objects comprise approximately 10% of the scene, the dynamic mode usually exhibits lower MAPE errors across all pixel distance ranges.

Beyond the average error, it is essential for predictions to offer meaningful guidance for navigation networks. Instead of

Fig. 7. Depth map predictions from different model pipelines, where white pixels correspond to null values.

focusing solely on pixel-level accuracy, depth predictions that are visually distinct are more effective in supporting decision-making. As shown in Fig. 7, the dynamic mode accurately predicts the vehicle’s forward motion, effectively separating it from the background and aligning more closely with human interpretation. Also visible in Fig. 7 are null pixels, which are unavoidable due to the global position of those pixels falling out of scope w.r.t. the reference frame. We note that a gap-filling algorithm can be used to fill null-pixel values to the nearest value. This makes an aesthetically pleasing depth map but adds significant computational overhead. Alternatively, we find that setting null values to 0, as reserved for erroneous values (see Section VI-C), has equal performance in terms of navigation accuracy than gap filling in such a way.

E. SmartDepth for Navigation

Fig. 8. *SmartDepth* results illustrating the trade-off between accuracy and efficiency as a function of X , the maximum allowed distance to use MADP.

Here we explore the parameter space and resulting error metrics for using *SmartDepth*, with navigation, to study the balance between accuracy and efficiency. Fig. 8 shows, and Table I lists, navigation accuracy, path length, execution time, mean power consumption, and expended energy versus X , the maximum allowed distance between the reference and proposed frames to use MADP – as defined in Equation 1. Each reported value is relative to a baseline model that does not use MADP (*i.e.*, $X = 0$). Relative navigation accuracy is

TABLE I

X [m]	β , accuracy	length	time	power	\dot{E} , energy
0	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
2	1.0506	1.1189	1.1004	0.9865	1.1002
4	1.0529	1.0959	1.0278	0.9517	1.0267
6	1.0198	1.1018	1.0224	0.9414	1.0212
8	0.9871	1.0734	0.8779	0.8399	0.8749
10	1.0038	1.1414	0.9466	0.8462	0.9436
12	0.9855	1.1219	0.8721	0.8109	0.8682
14	0.9978	1.1875	0.9080	0.7951	0.9037
16	0.9902	1.1219	0.8055	0.7411	0.8006
18	0.9899	1.1204	0.8234	0.7567	0.8188
20	0.9733	1.1008	0.8045	0.7518	0.7999

measured by the total ratio of all successful test paths between an arbitrary model and the baseline model, and is the term β in Equation 1. All other metrics were measured using only the set of test paths that were successful in both the baseline and model being compared against, using Equation 10:

$$\dot{u} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N \frac{u^{(i)}}{u_0^{(i)}} \quad (10)$$

where u is a variable representing either length, time, power, or energy, N is the number of test paths determined from the baseline model, $u^{(i)}$ is the value of a given variable measured when using an arbitrary model to navigate the i^{th} path, and $u_0^{(i)}$ is the value of a given variable when using the baseline model to navigate the i^{th} path. Equation 10 is used to calculate \dot{E} – as used in Equation 1. This normalization is used to mitigate biases resulting from various path characteristics, and to show relative performance w.r.t. the baseline model.

We use the direct depth sensors returned by AirSim as the reference frames for the MADP algorithm. There are various depth prediction models in literature that vary in accuracy – and these models will only improve. The differences in navigation accuracy, as compared to the depth sensors, show the worst-case scenario (relatively speaking in respect to MADP predictions) such that we assume the depth model is a perfect predictor, and we infer that an otherwise inferior depth model will result in theoretically smaller gaps in error. To get an estimate of computational costs, however, we use the frame-by-frame benchmarks found in Section VII-C and assume BTS was used for depth extraction.

The value of β in Equation 1 can be determined using Table I, which will consequently determine the value of X that is set before runtime and used by the navigation model. Determination of the value of X is very domain-dependent and out of the scope of this paper, and should include considerations into the application, environment, an ideally some cost function that quantifies the costs of each possible outcome. Future work may consider X as a prediction value that is dynamically and adaptively determined at run time.

Fig. 8 shows that the displayed metrics converge around $X = 16$ meters, after which the navigation accuracy drops below 1% of that from the baseline model. This corresponds to a value of $\beta = 0.9902$ in Equation 1, which results in

an overall decrease in navigation accuracy by 0.98%. As for the other error metrics that are measured on an path-by-path basis, setting $X = 16$ meters results in: increased path length by 12.19%, decreased execution time by 19.45%, decreased average power consumption by 25.89%, and decreased energy expenditure by 19.94%. These values represent the expected computational costs associated with each approach, which can be adjusted before runtime by selecting a different value for X . The user has the flexibility to prioritize higher efficiency, which comes with the trade-off of some degradation in navigation accuracy, or alternatively, choose to maximize navigation accuracy. This choice results in a 5.29% boost in navigation accuracy but at the cost of a 2.67% increase in energy expenditure. Interestingly, this increase in accuracy is sometimes observed when the data quality decreases, as is commonly seen in cases like quantization, likely due to some inherent form of generalization. It's also worth considering that the MADP algorithm might be introducing new information that the navigation neural network can leverage to improve its performance. Further, as shown in Fig. 8, the values for time, power, and energy are strongly correlated, which is why \bar{E} is used as the primary metric in Equation 1.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented *SmartDepth*, an intelligent technique for optimizing computing, by predicting future frames of 2D depth maps using our low-cost Motion-Aware Depth Prediction (MADP) algorithm. We have shown that our techniques are more efficient than using expensive depth extraction operations, such as image acquisition followed by a DNN – with improvements in execution time, average power consumption, and total energy expenditure. These improvements can be enhanced but come with an unavoidable trade-off in increased degradation to the resulting depth predictions. Our results warrant that *SmartDepth* is a flexible technique that effectively uses our MADP algorithm to improve not only a vehicle's sustained operation due to savings in energy expenditure, but also in the execution time to navigate a path, and in the power levels needed to execute depth-based operations – freeing up power for other operations. We posit that *SmartDepth* can have an impact in various robotics fields which use depth-based perception for decision-making logic, especially those with limited energy reservoirs and lightweight builds.

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